

Preparation and Use of Membrane Electrodes of Various Basic Salts of Denatured Deaminated Proteins for Determination of Cation Activities of Electrolytic Solutions: Part II. Deaminated Globin

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A cation exchanger, swelling slightly but insoluble in water, dilute solutions of mineral salts and alkaline solutions upto $pH 12$, has been prepared by the authors by deaminating denatured globin, separated from horse hemoglobin. Film membrane electrodes (1.2 to 1.5 mm thick) prepared from the basic salts of this cation exchanger, have been used for verification of Nernst equation for membrane potential in case of dilute aqueous solutions of chlorides of Na, Li, Ca, Ba and sulphate of Mg respectively. In case of monovalent cations, the Nernst equation holds good in the range of concentration 0.001 to 0.032M at molarity ratio 2 and 3, while with divalent cations the range is 0.0005 to 0.016M at molarity ratio 2, within an experimental error $\pm 3\%$.

In Part I, Pandit and Narwani¹ prepared a cation exchanger from denatured deaminated ovalbumin which disintegrated at pH higher than 8.0 as observed by one of the authors, Narwani, but not mentioned in Part I; hence its film membrane electrodes could not be used for determination of the cation activities of alkaline solutions from membrane potential measurement. The authors observed that the cation exchanger prepared from denatured deaminated globin did not dissolve in alkaline solutions upto pH^{12} and hence found it better suited for membrane potential measurement.

The object of the present work was (1) to prepare denatured globin from horse hemoglobin, (2) to deaminate the denatured globin and to prepare its sodium salt, (3) to study the ion exchange of this cation exchanger, (4) to prepare film membrane electrodes from various basic salts of this cation exchanger, (5) to study the influence of pH on the membrane potential, and (6) to verify Nernst equation for membrane potential,

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_2}{a_1}$$

in case of dilute aqueous solutions of chlorides of Na, K, Li, Ca and Ba and sulphate of Mg, using film membrane-electrodes made from respective basic salt of this cation exchanger, at various concentrations and molarity ratios.

EXPERIMENTAL

Denatured globin was separated from horse hemoglobin according to the method suggested by Anson and Mirsky². 10 g of horse hemoglobin were dissolved in 100 ml of

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1. D. R. Pandit and C. S. Narwani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 809.

2. M. Anson and A. E. Mirsky, *J. Gen. Physiology*, 1930, **13**, 121, 469.

0.05 *N* HCl and the solution treated with 2000 ml of acetone containing 20 ml of 1*N* HCl, whereby solution of heme and precipitate of globin were obtained. The precipitate of globin was dissolved in distilled water and treated with 1/3rd saturated solution of (NH₄)₂SO₄ to reprecipitate it; the precipitate was found to be insoluble in water; thus denatured globin was obtained. This precipitate of denatured globin was washed with distilled water to remove adhering (NH₄)₂SO₄. The denatured globin was found to be insoluble in water, 0.1*N* HCl, 1*N* solutions of alkali salts and various buffers upto pH 12; its isoelectric point was found to be pH 7.5 from the graph, giving relationship between pH and membrane potential, measured by the authors.

The powdered denatured globin was deaminated by treatment with a mixture of NaNO₂ and acetic acid at pH 4.0 for 8 days as suggested by Philpot and Small³ for any protein to convert—NH₂ to —OH with liberation of N₂; the deaminated globin was washed with distilled water till free from adhering NaNO₂ and was then treated with a solution of 0.1*N* NaCl brought to pH 8.0 with NaHCO₃: the product was sodium salt of deaminated denatured globin. The precipitate was filtered and washed with distilled water till free from Cl⁻. Other basic salts were prepared from the sodium salt by ion exchange, using 1*N* solution of chlorides, of K, Na, Li, Ca, Ba and sulphate of Mg. Semidry precipitate was compressed between metal plates covered with polythene sheets in a screw press for 48 hrs. to get thin uniform homogeneous membranes of thickness varying from 1.2 to 1.5 mm. Circular pieces of required diameter were cut and preserved in 0.1*N* solution of respective salts containing a crystal of thymol. The membrane electrodes obtained were quite tough and did not disintegrate or dissolve in water or salt solutions; they were not allowed to dry in air.

The influence of pH on membrane potential was studied to verify the complete deamination of the denatured globin; the film membrane of the sodium salt was placed between two solutions of NaCl, buffered to same known pH 4.0 to 11.7 as given by Conway⁴ for 0.1 and 0.2 ionic strengths and diluted 10 times with water to give 0.01 and 0.02 ionic strengths; the membrane potential was found to be constant.

For verification of Nernst equation for membrane potential, aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, LiCl, CaCl₂, BaCl₂ and MgSO₄ of concentrations varying from 0.001 to 0.064*M* at molarity ratios 2, 3 or 4, were used with the film membrane electrode of the corresponding salt of the denatured deaminated globin, following the same procedure as given in Part I. The time taken for reaching the Nernst potential value was about 15 to 20 mins; the e.m.f. remained constant for about 50 mins; on interchanging the solutions on the two sides of the membrane electrodes, there was no change in the membrane potential. The results for the monovalent cations are shown in Table I, and for the divalent cations in Table II.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table I shows that the obs. values of membrane potential agree within an experimental error of $\pm 3\%$ with those calculated from Nernst equation in case of solutions of electrolytes of different concentrations, containing the same critical monovalent cation on the two sides

3. Philpot and Small, *Biochem. J.*, 1938, **32**, 542.

4. B. C. Conway, *Electro-Chemical Data*, Ed., 1952, page 214.

TABLE I

Membrane potential (e.m.f. in mv) in case of aqueous solutions of various electrolytes containing monovalent cations at different concentrations and various molarity ratios, using film membrane electrodes of the corresponding basic salts of denatured deaminated globin, having different thickness as shown below.

Temp. of the Cell = $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$.

1. Electrolyte 2. Thickness of film	Cation activities Inside/Outside	Membrane potential	
		E(obs.) mv.	E(Cal.) mv.
1. NaCl	0.00193/0.00097	17.4	17.4
2. 1.21 mm.	0.00381/0.00193	17.5	17.4
3. Mol. Ratio	0.00746/0.00381	17.2	17.2
2 : 1	0.01454/0.00746	16.1	16.1
	0.02822/0.01454	16.7	16.9
	0.05395/0.02822	14.2	16.1
1. NaCl	0.00287/0.00097	27.1	27.7
2. 1.21 mm	0.00837/0.00287	26.8	27.3
3. Mol. Ratio	0.01366/0.00473	26.5	27.2
3 : 1	0.02655/0.00928	26.0	26.1
	0.05094/0.01804	23.8	26.6
1. NaCl	0.00381/0.00097	35.2	34.9
2. 1.21 mm	0.00746/0.00193	34.9	34.7
3. Mol. Ratio	0.01454/0.00381	34.7	34.3
4 : 1	0.02822/0.00746	33.6	34.1
	0.05395/0.01454	29.6	33.6
1. KCl	0.00193/0.00097	17.0	17.4
2. 1.43 mm	0.00381/0.00193	17.1	17.4
3. Mol. Ratio	0.00745/0.00381	17.1	17.4
2 : 1	0.01451/0.00745	16.9	17.1
	0.02810/0.01451	16.7	16.9
	0.05357/0.02810	14.6	16.5
1. KCl	0.00287/0.00097	27.4	27.7
2. 1.43 mm	0.00835/0.00287	27.0	27.3
3. Mol. Ratio	0.01363/0.00473	26.7	27.1
3 : 1	0.02646/0.00926	26.2	26.9
	0.05052/0.01798	22.4	26.4

TABLE I (Contd.)

1. KCl	0.00381/0.00097	35.3	34.9
2. 1.43 mm	0.01451/0.00381	34.4	34.3
3. Mol. Ratio	0.02810/0.00745	34.2	34.0
4 : 1	0.05357/0.01451	31.4	33.4
1. LiCl	0.00193/0.00097	17.6	17.5
2. 1.32 mm	0.00382/0.00193	17.6	17.5
3. Mol. Ratio	0.00750/0.00382	17.0	17.3
2 : 1	0.01463/0.00750	16.9	17.1
	0.02845/0.01463	16.7	17.0
	0.05498/0.02844	12.3	16.9
1. LiCl	0.00288/0.00098	28.0	27.8
2. 1.32 mm	0.00840/0.00288	27.4	27.4
3. Mol. Ratio	0.01374/0.00474	27.1	27.2
3 : 1	0.02676/0.00929	26.5	27.1
	0.05172/0.01814	21.7	26.7

TABLE II

Membrane potential (e.m.f. in mv) in case of various electrolytes containing divalent cations at different concentrations using film membrane electrodes of the corresponding basic salts of denatured deaminated globin.

Temp. of the Cell = $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$.

1. Electrolytes 2. Molarity Ratio	Cation activities Inside/Outside	Membrane potential	
		E(Obs.) mv.	E(Cal.) mv.
1. CaCl ₂	0.00091/0.00047	8.6	8.5
2. 2 : 1	0.00174/0.00091	8.5	8.4
	0.00330/0.00174	8.2	8.2
	0.00612/0.00330	7.8	7.9
	0.01128/0.00612	7.6	7.8
	0.01949/0.01128	4.7	7.0
1. BaCl ₂	0.00090/0.00047	8.7	8.5
2. 2 : 1	0.00174/0.00090	8.3	8.3
	0.00329/0.00174	8.3	8.2
	0.00610/0.00329	8.0	7.9
	0.01117/0.00610	7.2	7.4
	0.01920/0.01117	4.8	6.9

TABLE II (Contd.)

1. MgSO_4	0.00091/0.00047	8.4	8.4
2. 2 : 1	0.00174/0.00091	8.3	8.3
	0.00331/0.00174	8.2	8.2
	0.00619/0.00331	8.1	8.0
	0.01141/0.00619	7.6	7.8
	0.02051/0.01141	4.9	7.5

of the film membrane of the corresponding basic salt of the deaminated denatured globin. It is observed that the range of concentration at which there is an agreement between the observed and the calculated values of the membrane potential is for all monovalent cations (Na^+ , K^+ , Li^+) 0.001 to 0.032M, at molarity ratio 2 and 3. Table II shows that in case of bivalent cations Ca^{++} , Ba^{++} and Mg^{++} , the range of concentration within which there is an agreement between the observed and the calculated values of the membrane potential is 0.001 to 0.016M, at molarity ratio 2.

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